

Blood profile of Balinese male ducks given papaya leaf extract (*Carica papaya* L) through drinking water

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Abstract

Papaya leaf water extract (*Carica papaya* L) contains flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and beta-carotene, which are herbal feed additives for ducks. This study aims to examine the benefits of papaya leaf water extract through drinking water in improving the blood lipid profile of male Bali ducks. This study was conducted in Kerambitan, Tabanan, Bali, for 10 weeks. This study used a completely randomized design (CRD) with four treatments and five replicates, each experimental unit using five male Bali ducks weighing 46.04 ± 2.21 grams. The four treatments were drinking water without papaya leaf extract (A); drinking water with 2% papaya leaf extract (B); drinking water with 4% papaya leaf extract (C); and drinking water with 6% papaya leaf extract (D). The variables measured were total cholesterol, triglycerides, HDL, and LDL. The results obtained from this study were that total cholesterol, triglycerides, HDL, and LDL in the four treatments were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The conclusion from the results of this study is that the administration of papaya leaf extract at levels of 2%, 4%, and 6% had no effect on the blood lipid profile of Bali ducks.

Keywords: Blood Lipid Profile; Papaya Leaf Water Extract; Male Balinese Ducks; Herbal Feed Additive; Cholesterol; And Triglycerides

1. Introduction

Bali ducks are one of the local poultry germplasm that have strategic value, both as a source of animal protein and in the socio-cultural role of Balinese society [1]. However, duck meat tends to have a higher fat content than other poultry, which can potentially affect meat quality and consumer preferences [2]. Blood lipid profiles, which include total cholesterol, triglycerides, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL), are important indicators of livestock metabolic health and are closely related to meat product quality [3].

In an effort to improve the quality of poultry products, the use of plant-based natural feed additives (phytogenic) is one alternative to be explored. Phytogenics are known to contain bioactive compounds with antioxidant, antimicrobial, and hypolipidemic activities [4]. Previous studies have shown that administering noni juice (*Morinda citrifolia*) can reduce cholesterol levels in local chickens [5], while a combination of turmeric extract (*Curcuma domestica*) and red dragon fruit (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) can affect the lipid profile of broiler chickens [3].

Papaya leaves (*Carica papaya* L.) are one of the herbal plants rich in bioactive compounds, such as papain, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and β -carotene [7, 8]. Various studies have reported that the use of papaya leaves in the form of fermentation or extract can improve production performance, reduce abdominal fat, and affect the organoleptic characteristics of local poultry meat [9–12]. Recent studies also show that fermented papaya leaf water extract administered through drinking water can improve the appearance of Balitbangtan superior native chickens (KUB) [13].

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However, studies on the effect of papaya leaf water extract administered through drinking water on the blood lipid profile of male bali ducks are still limited. Administration in liquid form generally has higher bioavailability than powder or flour form because the active substances are more easily and quickly absorbed by the digestive tract [14]. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the effect of papaya leaf water extract through drinking water on the blood lipid profile of male bali ducks, including total cholesterol, triglycerides, HDL, and LDL.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

This study was conducted over a period of 10 weeks in Kerambitan, Tabanan, Bali. The ducks used were 100 male bali ducks aged 5 days with an average weight of 46.04 ± 2.21 g, obtained from a breeder in Kediri Tabanan. The cages used in this study were battery colony cages, with 20 cage compartments. The feed used consisted of several ingredients, namely duck concentrate 144 as a source of protein and corn and rice bran as a source of energy. Feed and drinking water were provided ad libitum. The drinking water provided contained papaya leaf extract according to the treatment.

2.2. The Process of Making Papaya Leaf Extract

The papaya leaves used were mature green leaves, which were cut, mixed with water at a 1:1 ratio, blended, and then filtered to separate the leaf residue from the papaya leaf extract.

Table 1 Phytochemical constituents of papaya leaf extract

No	Parameter	Methods	Units	Results
1	Flavonoids	Spektrofotometri	mg QE/100 g	177.70
2	Tannins	Spektrofotometri	mg TAE/ 100 g	548.78
5	Beta-carotene	Spektrofotometri	mg β -karoten/100 g	2798.42
3	Saponins	Spektrofotometri		+
4	Alkaloids	Spektrofotometri		-

Source: Laboratory Test Report of Food Analysis, Faculty of Agricultural Technology, Udayana University (2022)

2.3. Experimental Design

The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized design (CRD) consisting of 4 treatments and 5 replicates, where each replicate consisted of 5 male bali ducks weighing 46.04 ± 2.21 g. The four treatments were drinking water without papaya leaf extract (A), drinking water with 2% papaya leaf extract (B), drinking water with 4% papaya leaf extract (C), and drinking water with 6% papaya leaf extract (D).

2.4. Observed Variables

The variables observed were total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and triglycerides. Blood samples were taken at the end of the study from the wing via the brachial vein using a syringe and then placed in an EDTA tube. Sample analysis to measure blood cholesterol levels used the enzymatic colorimetric (CHOD-PAP) cholesterol oxidase-phenol-aminophenazone method, while blood triglyceride levels were measured using the enzymatic colorimetric (GPO-PAP) glycerol-3-phosphate-oxidase-phenol-aminophenazone method [15].

2.5. Data Analysis

At the end of the study, the data obtained were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). When significant differences among treatments were observed ($P < 0.05$), the analysis was continued with Duncan's multiple range test [16]

3. Results and Discussion

The results showed that the average total cholesterol levels of male bali ducks in treatments A (drinking water without papaya leaf extract), B (2%), C (4%), and D (6%) did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$). This may be due to the flavonoid compounds in papaya leaf extract not being sufficient to inhibit the HMG-CoA reductase enzyme. According to [17], flavonoids can inhibit cholesterol synthesis by acting as HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, reducing acyl-CoA cholesterol acyltransferase (ACAT) activity, and decreasing cholesterol absorption in the digestive tract. However, this finding differs from [18], which reported that supplementation of 4–5% noni extract significantly reduced total cholesterol in superior native chickens.

Table 2 Blood cholesterol of male bali ducks given papaya leaf extract in drinking water

Variabel	Treatment ¹⁾				SEM ²⁾
	A	B	C	D	
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	195.91 ^a	175.09 ^a	173.92 ^a	168.53 ^a	7.34
HDL (mg/dL)	141.31 ^a	158.85 ^a	161.39 ^a	167.95 ^a	4.12
LDL (mg/dL)	28.63 ^a	13.32 ^a	24.30 ^a	19.25 ^a	3.15
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	129.89 ^a	132.06 ^a	135.68 ^a	140.18 ^a	4.08

Notes: Drinking water with 0% papaya leaf extract (A), drinking water with 2% papaya leaf extract (B), drinking water with 4% papaya leaf extract (C), and drinking water with 6% papaya leaf extract (D); SEM = Standard Error of the Treatment Mean.; Values with different letters in the same row indicate non-significant differences ($P > 0.05$).

As shown in Table 2, supplementation with papaya leaf extract at 2%, 4%, and 6% did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) increase HDL levels in male bali ducks, which ranged from 158.85 to 167.95 mg/dL. This may be attributed to the similar blood cholesterol concentrations among treatments. [19] reported that HDL levels are associated with cholesterol concentrations and the synthesis of steroid compounds and bile salts. Another study suggested that optimal HDL levels in ducks are >60 mg/dL [20]. These results are consistent with [21], which found that supplementation with a mixture of turmeric and dragon fruit peel extract at 4% did not sufficiently increase HDL in broiler chickens.

Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) is considered bad cholesterol because it is atherogenic, easily adhering to blood vessel walls and promoting fat accumulation and vascular narrowing [22]. Supplementation with papaya leaf extract at 2–6% did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) reduce LDL levels compared to treatment A (Table 2). This was likely due to similar HDL concentrations across treatments. LDL and HDL play opposite roles in regulating cholesterol metabolism: LDL increases deposition, whereas HDL promotes disposal [23]. The LDL levels observed in this study (13.32–24.30 mg/dL) were below the reference level reported by [24], which states that the normal LDL concentration in ducks is <130 mg/dL.

The average triglyceride concentration in treatment A was 129.89 mg/dL, while treatments B, C, and D were 1.67%, 4.46%, and 7.92% higher, respectively, with no statistically significant differences ($P > 0.05$) (Table 2). This is consistent with the total cholesterol levels being similar across treatments. These findings align with [25], which reported that 6% papaya leaf extract in drinking water did not increase final body weight in ducks. Physiologically, triglycerides serve as an energy reserve stored in adipose tissue, contributing to weight gain [26].

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the addition of papaya leaf water extract at levels of 2–6% through drinking water had no effect on the blood lipid profile of male bali ducks.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

We declare that there is no conflict of interest with any financial organization related to the material discussed in this paper.

Statement of ethical approval

The animal ethics committee has approved 100 Bali duck male (5 day old) used in this study from the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Udayana University, Badung, Bali, Indonesia.

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